

**ALIGNED CARBON NANOTUBES FOR MULTIFUNCTIONAL
NANOCOMPOSITES AND NANODEVICES:**

**Multicomponent Micropatterned
Aligned Carbon Nanotube Devices with Reversibly Switchable
Electronic Properties for Multifunctional Applications**

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ABSTRACT

A simple, but effective and versatile, double contact transfer method was developed for controlled fabrication of three-dimensional (3D) multicomponent micropatterns of vertically-aligned carbon nanotubes. Using our reported dry contact transfer technique,¹² we first built a micropattern of vertically-aligned multiwalled carbon nanotubes (VA-MWNTs) onto a Scotch tape. The pre-transferred VA-MWNT pattern was then used as a new physical mask for the second dry contact transfer of vertically-aligned single-walled carbon nanotubes (VA-SWNTs) of a different length. The resultant 3D micropatterns with VA-SWNTs interposed into the VA-MWNT patterned structure was demonstrated to show reversible electrical responses of potential applications in various electronic devices, ranging from touch sensors to electronic switches.

KEYWORDS

Vertically-aligned carbon nanotube, contact transfer, 3-D micropattern, switchable electronics

Carbon nanotubes (CNTs) in an aligned and micropatterned form are highly desirable for many device applications, ranging from nanoscale sensors to electronic circuits [1-3]. Although various micropatterning methods, including photolithography [4-6], soft lithography [7, 8], and electron or laser beam lithography [9, 10], have been devised for producing single component vertically-aligned CNT micropatterns for some years, the formation of multicomponent vertically-aligned CNT micropatterns is a recent development. In this context, we have reported the preparation of multicomponent micropatterns of VA-MWNTs interposed with nanoparticles [11], self-assembled nonaligned CNTs [12], or VA-SWNTs [13]. In the present study, we developed a double contact transfer technique by using a patterned structure of VA-MWNTs pre-transferred onto a Scotch tape [11] as a physical mask for the second dry contact transfer of, for example, vertically-aligned single-walled carbon nanotubes (VA-SWNTs) of a different length to produce three-dimensional (3D) aligned CNT micropatterns with VA-SWNTs interposed into the VA-MWNT patterned structure. Here, we report the detailed procedures of the newly-developed double contact transfer technique for the formation of 3D multicomponent micropatterns with VA-SWNTs interposed into the VA-MWNT patterned structure, and demonstrate their potential applications in micro-/nano-electronic devices.

Figure 1 shows a schematic representation of the procedures for fabricating 3D VA-SWNT/VA-MWNT multicomponent micropatterns by the newly-developed double contact transfer technique. To start with, we synthesized nonpatterned VA-MWNT films with a homogenous tube length of $\sim 5 \mu\text{m}$ on a quartz glass plate by pyrolysis of iron phthalocyanine (FePc) in Ar/H₂ atmosphere at 1100°C [14]. Nonpatterned VA-SWNT films with a uniform length of about 10-15 μm were also synthesized by plasma enhanced chemical vapor deposition according to an earlier publication [15].

FIG. 1. A schematic illustration of the double contact transfer method.

Following a published procedure [12], we adhered a TEM grid consisting of square windows (*ca.* 100- μm wide) onto a commercially available Scotch tape (3M, polypropylene-film-supported acrylic adhesive) as a physical mask (Fig. 1a) for the first dry contact transfer of VA-MWNT micropatterns from the *as-synthesized* nonpatterned VA-MWNT film (Fig. 1b) [11, 16]. After careful removal of the TEM grid, a VA-MWNT micropattern replicated the TEM grid structure

formed on the Scotch tape (Fig. 1c), which was then used as a new physical mask for the second dry contact transfer of VA-SWNT micropatterns from the *as-synthesized* nonpatterned VA-SWNT film (Fig. 1d). Finally, a 3D multicomponent micropattern with VA-SWNTs interposed into the VA-MWNT patterned structure was obtained on the flexible Scotch tape (Fig. 1e). Figures 2a and b show the positive and negative VA-MWNT micropatterns on the original quartz plate and Scotch tape, respectively, formed by the first dry contact transfer (*cf.* Fig. 1b). Upon the second dry contact transfer by using the Scotch-tape-supported VA-MWNT micropattern (*i.e.* Fig. 2b) as a physical mask, a 3D multicomponent micropattern with VA-SWNTs interposed into the VA-MWNT patterned structure was formed on the flexible Scotch tape (Fig. 2d) whilst the VA-SWNTs in the regions covered by the nonadhesive VA-MWNT square patterns were left over on the quartz substrate used for the synthesis of VA-SWNTs (Figs. 2c & 1d). While Figure 2d clearly shows that both the contact-transferred VA-MWNTs and VA-SWNTs are well registered into their respective areas, the corresponding SEM images under higher magnifications (Figs. 2e & f) reveal that both the VA-MWNTs and VA-SWNTs remain perpendicularly-aligned in full lengths even after the contact transfer for twice. This is because aligned CNTs have been previously demonstrated to possess excellent mechanical flexibility [15, 17, 18] and the dry contact transfer did not cause any obvious detrimental effect on their alignment [11, 16].

Unlike the 3D single-component VA-MWNT micropatterns [16], the *newly-prepared* 3D multicomponent micropattern with VA-SWNTs region-selectively interposed into the VA-MWNT patterned structure showed interesting region-specific electronic properties characteristic of the micropatterned *semiconducting* SWNTs and *metallic* MWNTs, respectively [13]. Therefore, these 3D VA-MWNT/VA-SWNT micropatterns should be useful for the development of various novel electronic devices for a wide range of potential applications.

FIG. 2. SEM images of the aligned MWNTs left over on the quartz substrate (a) and transferred onto the Scotch tape (b) after the 1st dry contact transfer; the aligned SWNTs left over on the quartz substrate (c) and the hybrid pattern of aligned SWNTs/MWNTs transferred onto the Scotch tape (d) after the 2nd dry contact transfer. (e, f) as for (d) under higher magnifications.

To demonstrate potential applications for the newly-prepared 3D VA-MWNT/VA-SWNT multicomponent micropatterns, we replaced the Scotch tape with a conductive adhesive tape (*e.g.* copper conducting adhesive tape, 3M) for the double contact transfer (Fig. 1) and placed a conducting ITO glass plate on the top surface of the resultant 3D nanotube pattern to form the top electrode (Fig. 3a). As the VA-SWNTs are longer than the interposed VA-MWNTs, a current (I) – voltage (V) curve characteristic of the semiconducting VA-SWNTs was observed initially (curve i in Fig. 3c). Upon compression by pressing down the ITO glass (*ca.* 100g loading, Fig. 3b), an effective contact between the VA-MWNTs and ITO glass was made while the VA-SWNTs were mechanically compressed [15]. As a result, an Ohmic $I - V$ behavior was obtained (curve ii in Fig. 3c) as the metallic VA-MWNTs supported the major current flow between the two electrodes in the compression state. Due to the reversible mechanical compressibility of the VA-SWNTs [15, 17, 18], we found that $I - V$ characteristics of the 3D multicomponent micropattern with the shorter VA-MWNTs interposed into the longer VA-SWNTs can be reversibly switched between the metallic and semiconducting states during the compression-decompression cycles. Under a constant voltage (say, 5 V), a strong current response (by a factor of 2) to compression-decompression cycles was observed, which is apparently very fast with a good repeatability (Fig. 3d). Inset of Fig. 3d shows an enlarged view for a small portion of the current response curve. The peak current intensity and response time can be tuned by developing the 3D VA-MWNT/VA-SWNT multicomponent micropatterns with various patterned geometries and/or nanotube length differences. These *newly-developed* 3D multicomponent VA-MWNT/VA-SWNT micropatterns with reversibly switchable electronic properties can be potentially useful for many device applications, including touch sensors, memory storages, and electronic switches.

FIG. 3. (a & b) Schematic illustrations of the 3D VA-MWNT/VA-SWNT multicomponent micropatterns at the decompression and compression state, respectively, (c) Current-voltage response corresponding to (a) and (b), and (d) Current response to the compression-decompression cycles at a voltage of 5 V. Tested pattern area: 1mm^2 .

In summary, we have developed a simple, but very versatile, double contact dry transfer technique for controlled fabrication of 3D multicomponent micropatterns with VA-SWNTs interposed into the VA-MWNT patterned structure. The resultant 3D VA-MWNT/VA-SWNT multicomponent micropatterns with region-specific nanotube lengths can be reversibly switched between a semiconducting and metallic state characteristic of the semiconducting VA-SWNTs and metallic VA-MWNTs, respectively. The observed fast and highly reversible pulsed current response to compression-decompression cycles at a constant voltage clearly indicate that these *newly-developed* 3D VA-MWNT/VA-SWNT multicomponent micropatterns are useful in a large

variety of micro-/nano-electronic devices, ranging from electronic switches through memory storages to touch sensors. Furthermore, the double contact transfer concept developed in this study should be applicable for interposing a large variety of multicomponent elements (e.g. nanotubes, nanowires, quantum dots, photonic crystals, metal oxides) onto a single chip for various multifunctional device applications.

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References

- [1] Dresselhaus, M.S.; Dai, H.J. Recent advances in methods of forming carbon nanotubes. *MRS Bulletin* **2004**, *29*, 244-250.
- [2] Qu, L.; Peng, Q.; Dai, L.; Spinks, G.M.; Wallace, G.G.; Baughman, R.H. Carbon nanotube electroactive polymer materials: Opportunities and challenges. *MRS Bulletin* **2008**, *33*, 215-224.
- [3] Dai, L. (Ed.), “*Carbon Nanotechnology: Recent Developments in Chemistry, Physics, Materials Science and Device Applications*”, Elsevier: Amsterdam, 2006.
- [4] Fan, S.; Chapline, M.G.; Franklin, N.R.; Tomblor, T.W.; Cassell, A.M.; Dai, H.J. Self-oriented regular arrays of carbon nanotubes and their field emission properties. *Science* **1999**, *283*, 512-514.
- [5] Yang, Y.; Huang, S.; He, H.; Mau, A. W. H.; Dai, L. Patterned growth of well-aligned carbon nanotubes: A photolithographic approach. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **1999**, *121*, 10832-10833.
- [6] Zhang, Z. J.; Wei, B. Q.; Ramanath, G.; Ajayan, P. M. Substrate-site selective growth of aligned carbon nanotubes. *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **2000**, *77*, 3764-3766.

- [7] Xia, Y.; Whitesides, G. M. Soft lithography. *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **1998**, *37*, 551-575.
- [8] Huang, S.; Mau, A. W. H.; Turney, T. W.; White, P. A.; Dai, L. Patterned growth of well-aligned carbon nanotubes: A soft-lithographic approach. *J. Phys. Chem. B* **2000**, *104*, 2193-2196.
- [9] Wei, H.; Kim, S. N.; Marcus, H. L.; Papadimitrakopoulos, F. Preferential forest assembly of single-wall carbon nanotubes on low-energy electron-beam patterned nafion films. *Chem. Mater.* **2006**, *18*, 1100-1106.
- [10] Hung, W. H.; Kumar, R.; Bushmaker, A.; Cronin, S. B.; Bronikowski, M. J. Rapid prototyping of three-dimensional microstructures from multiwalled carbon nanotubes. *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **2007**, *91*, 093121.
- [11] Yang, J.; Qu, L.; Zhao, Y.; Zhang, Q.; Dai, L.; Baur, J. W.; Maruyama, B.; Vaia, R. A.; Shin, E.; Murray, P. T.; Luo, H.; Guo, Z. Multicomponent and multidimensional carbon nanotube micropatterns by dry contact transfer. *J. Nanosci. Nanotechnol.* **2007**, *7*, 1573-1580.
- [12] Yang, J.; Dai, L.; Vaia, R. A. Multicomponent interposed carbon nanotube micropatterns by region-specific contact transfer and self-assembling. *J. Phys. Chem. B* **2003**, *107*, 12387-12390.
- [13] Qu, L. T.; Dai, L. Direct growth of three-dimensional multicomponent micropatterns of vertically aligned single-walled carbon nanotubes interposed with their multi-walled counterparts on Al-activated iron substrates. *J. Mater. Chem.* **2007**, *17*, 3401-3405.
- [14] Huang, S.; Dai, L.; Mau, A. W. H. Patterned growth and contact transfer of well-aligned carbon nanotube films. *J. Phys. Chem. B* **1999**, *103*, 4223-.
- [15] Qu, L.T.; Dai, L. Gecko-foot-mimetic aligned single-walled carbon nanotube dry adhesives with unique electrical and thermal properties. *Adv. Mater.* **2007**, *19*, 3844-3849.

- [16] Patil, A.; Ohashi, T.; Buldum, A.; Dai, L. Controlled preparation and electron emission properties of three-dimensional micropatterned aligned carbon nanotubes. *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **2006**, *89*, 103103.
- [17] Cao, A. Y.; Dickrell, P. L.; Sawyer, W. G.; Ghasemi-Nejhad, M. N.; Ajayan, P. M. Super-compressible foamlike carbon nanotube films. *Science* **2005**, *310*, 1307-1310.
- [18] Suhr, J.; Victor, P.; Sreekala, L. C. S.; Zhang, X.; Nalamasu, O.; Ajayan, P. M. Fatigue resistance of aligned carbon nanotube arrays under cyclic compression. *Nat. Nanotech.* **2007**, *2*, 417-421.